

Microstructure and Properties of Sputter Deposited Cu/Nb Microlaminates

S. P. Rawal, G. M. Swanson, W. C. Moshier

Martin Marietta Astronautics, P. O. Box 179, Denver, Colorado 80201

K.S. Kumar

Martin Marietta Labs, 1450 So Rolling Road, Baltimore, MD 21220

ABSTRACT

The Cu/Nb microlaminates were produced by sputter depositing the constituent materials onto a Cu substrate both at room temperature and elevated temperature (500°C). To determine the effect of Nb volume fraction on the composites' properties, two types of microlaminates were constructed by depositing alternating layers of Cu and Nb. These microlaminates included: (i) Cu/50%Nb 1:1, and (ii) Cu/25%Nb 3:1; fabricated with 100 nm thick Nb layers. Selected area diffraction obtained from a TEM investigation confirmed that both Cu and Nb layers exhibited polycrystalline structure in the as-deposited microlaminates. These diffraction patterns also suggested the presence of a residual stress state in microlaminates deposited on the 500°C substrate. Each microlaminate exhibited a the elastic modulus values similar to the values obtained by rule-of-mixture. The RT deposited microlaminates consistently indicated microhardness values higher than the hardness values for the corresponding microlaminates deposited at the elevated temperature, indicating the presence of a comparatively dense and fine substructure in RT microlaminates. This paper presents the results describing the role of the percentage Nb, layer thickness, and the substrate temperature on the deposition morphology, and material properties of high strength, high conductivity Cu/Nb microlaminates.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advanced materials which offer the combination of high strength and high thermal or electrical conductivity attributes at elevated temperatures are required for several applications (1-3) such as high power generators, space propulsion systems, heat exchangers, and high field magnets. Copper (Cu) is most often the cost-effective choice due to its high inherent conductivities but its strength decreases as the operational temperature increases. Because refractory metals typically have high strength at elevated temperatures, high temperature mechanical properties are improved by incorporating fine dispersions of refractory metals such as niobium (Nb), tantalum (Ta), chromium (Cr), or tungsten (W) in the Cu matrix, thus only slightly reducing the thermal/electrical conductivity. Of these Cu-refractory metal systems, the Cu-Nb system offers the best combination of specific conductivity, and high temperature strength.

Both deformation processing (4-5) and physical vapor deposition (6-8) methods have been used to obtain fine dispersions of niobium (typical volume fraction ≤ 0.2) in the form of fine particles, ribbons, or filaments in the fabrication of Cu-Nb microcomposites. These microcomposites produced from a precursor billet (by mechanical alloying or melting and casting) with subsequent deformation processing exhibit high strength, but they are prone to contamination by metallic and non-metallic inclusions at the various stages of precursor preparation and subsequent multiple processing steps. In contrast, sputtering provides a unique way to produce contamination-free in-

situ microcomposites or microlaminates with fine grain material. Earlier studies of sputter-deposited *thin-film* metallic microlaminates, such as Cu-Ni (9), Au-Ni (10), and Cu-Nb (8,11,12), indicated the existence of a "supermodulus effect" in which a 2 to 5-fold increase of biaxial and flexural moduli was reported with modulation wavelengths, (i.e., bilayer thickness) in the range of 2 nm. Attempts to reproduce the supermodulus effect have been largely unsuccessful as more recent measurements show that superlattice elastic constants are often equal or slightly less than the homogeneous alloys. However, substantial increases in hardness and yield strength have been reported in superlattices and transition metal nitride superlattices suggesting the importance of the role of the film microstructure and composite architecture.

While the microlaminates with layer thicknesses less than 10 nm have the potential to exhibit supermodulus and superhardness effects, the key focus of this investigation was to develop sputter-deposition conditions to produce clean microlaminates with layer thicknesses ≥ 100 nm and determine the effect of Nb volume fraction, and thickness of alternating layers on the strength, toughness, and electrical conductivity. This paper discusses the microstructure and mechanical properties of the sputter deposited Cu/Nb microlaminates constructed from alternating layers of crystalline Cu and Nb (100 nm in each microlaminate) with layer thickness ratios of 1:1 and 3:1.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A. Material Processing

The Cu/Nb microlaminates were successfully fabricated using a sputter deposition process. Materials were deposited in a three cathode RF/DC magnetron sputtering system with a sputter-down cathode configuration. Nb and Cu were sputtered using DC potentials, with the cathodes co-focused onto the copper substrate at 60° from the substrate normal while the substrate was rotated at 20 rpm. Deposition rates were determined by sputtering Nb and Cu separately onto optically flat sapphire substrates. Deposition of these materials was performed at two different temperatures: (1) room temperature (RT), and (2) 500°C , to obtain the desired crystal structure.

Cu/Nb microlaminates were deposited onto a Cu foil substrate. Substrate temperature was controlled by heating the back surface of the Cu foil through a tungsten wire serpentine in an alumina holder which was separated from the substrate by a quartz window and a Cu platen. A control thermocouple was attached to the back surface of the quartz window. After establishing the process parameters such as substrate temperature ($\approx 500^\circ\text{C}$, i.e., $0.57 T_m$ for Cu or $0.28 T_m$ for Nb), composite structure, bulk chemistry, and deposition parameters through various rate runs, several Cu/Nb microlaminates were fabricated. The Cu/Nb microlaminates were fabricated with two different architectures: (1) Cu/50% Nb (i.e., 1:1) constructed from alternating layers (100 nm thick each) of Cu and Nb, and (2) Cu/25% Nb (i.e., 3:1) constructed from alternating layers of 300 nm thick Cu and 100 nm thick Nb to a total thickness of 25 μm .

B. Material Characterization

Cross-sectional transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to evaluate the interface between the Cu and Nb layers as well as the microstructure of each layer. Thin foils of the microlaminate were examined using a Phillips CM30 with an acceleration voltage of 300 kV. Bright field images and selected area diffraction patterns were obtained to characterize the microlaminate microstructure. Deposited film thickness, particle morphology and fine porosity in the microlaminates were examined by using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Microlaminate/

substrate cross sections were mounted in epoxy and polished to a 1- μm finish, coated with 10 nm of gold, and analyzed using a 20 kV accelerating voltage.

C. Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties (e.g., elastic modulus, microhardness, tensile and compressive strengths) of the as-deposited films were evaluated, without removing them from their substrates. Nanoindentation was used to determine the Young's modulus and hardness values of each film. Specific details of the nanoindentation test technique are documented in the literature (13). Using the Berkovitch indenter in the displacement control mode, each specimen was indented ten times at four different depth (displacement) levels: 50, 100, 500, and 1000 nm.

Tension tests of the thin film materials were performed using non-contact displacement sensors. The system calibration was made by testing annealed Cu foils that were identical to the substrate foils used for the microlaminates. Test results were used to estimate the elastic modulus, yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and strain to failure values. Vickers microhardness (H_v) measurements were made by making a minimum of 12 indents at applied loads between 25 and 200 g. Compressive yield strength (σ_{y^c}) values were derived from the measured H_v values, using the relationship $\sigma_{y^c} = H_v/3$. Each indentation was examined under SEM to determine the average diagonal size to calculate the H_v value, and also to examine the apparent mode of deformation, and detect any potential microcracks (at the tips of the diagonals), thus providing a measure of the toughness of as deposited film materials.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Deposition Morphology

The cross-sectional view (Figure 1) of a Cu/Nb microlaminate shows the columnar grain structure where the individual columns are separated by voids. This columnar grain structure is a typical film morphology and structure which results where each column appears to be 1.5-2 μm wide surrounded by a thin (0.02 μm) void region. Figure 1 also shows a good adherent bond at the film/substrate interface. The surface morphology of the microlaminate revealed irregular shaped agglomerates (1.5-2 μm) that form at the tip of the columnar structure separated by the microvoids.

Bright field TEM images (Figure 2) of as-deposited Cu/Nb microlaminates reveal the nearly uniform thickness and microscopic waviness of each layer. In each case the Nb layer has a relatively darker contrast compared to the Cu layer. These images confirm the 100 nm/layer thickness in the Cu/Nb 1:1 microlaminate (Figure 2a), and 300 nm thick Cu layer and 100 nm thick Nb layer in Cu/Nb 3:1 microlaminate (Figure 2b). Each individual layer is clearly distinguishable, and both the layers and interfaces are free from any particles, or other contaminants that could easily degrade the properties of the microlaminate. The microlaminate deposited at 500°C do not form any reaction product at the Cu/Nb interface. The selected area diffraction (SAD) patterns obtained from each microlaminate, as shown in Figure 3, reveal a spotty ring pattern which corresponds to the polycrystalline Cu and Nb layers. These SAD patterns also indicate the effect of substrate temperature on deposition morphology both in terms of texture, and lattice distortion due to residual stresses. The microlaminates processed on the high temperature substrate reveal a more textured deposit, suggesting a preferred orientation in the deposited layers compared to the microlaminates deposited on the RT substrate. Also, because of the high processing temperature,

and differences in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between Cu (CTE=16.5 ppm/K) and Nb (7.31 ppm/K), a tensile residual stress is anticipated in the Cu layers and a corresponding compressive residual stress is anticipated in the Nb layers when the high temperature microlaminate is cooled from 500°C to RT. These residual stresses in the microlaminate distort the respective lattice, as evidenced by the slightly larger ring diameter in the SAD patterns of high temperature microlaminates compared to the same architecture deposited on RT substrate. Further TEM examination of each microlaminate also revealed the presence of fine grain structure (50-70 nm size grains, and a few (annealing) twins in the Cu layers) in constituent Cu and Nb layers.

B. Mechanical Properties

Both the elastic modulus and hardness values of the as-deposited film (on the Cu substrate) were obtained from the load-displacement curves corresponding to indentation depths ranging from 50 to 1000 nm. Measured hardness and modulus values are not influenced by the presence of the substrate because the maximum indentation depth of 1000 nm is only 4% of the total microlaminate thickness.

Elastic Modulus—The average elastic modulus of each as-sputtered film at indentation depths between 50 and 1000 nm is shown in Figure 4. Average elastic modulus values of 115-120 GPa for the Cu/Nb 1:1 microlaminates (200-1000 nm indentation depths) are quite consistent with the 100 GPa value obtained from the tension test results, and the 110 GPa value obtained from the rule-of-mixture (ROM). Also, the elastic modulus of 112-119 GPa for the Cu/Nb 3:1 microlaminate is in good agreement with the ROM modulus value of 112 GPa. The agreement between the measured and ROM elastic modulus values for these microlaminates indicates that the extent of porosity trapped during sputtering in these multilayer architectures, constructed with thin alternating layers of Cu and Nb, is definitely lower ($\leq 10\%$) than thick monolithic Cu and Nb foil materials.

Hardness and Strength—Hardness measurements of these as-sputtered films were performed both by Nanoindentation and Vickers microhardness test methods. In the absence of any well-established relationship between the nanohardness and Vickers microhardness values, both the results are discussed here.

Nanohardness—Figure 5 shows the nanohardness values of each film material at indent depths between 50-1000 nm. Results of these nanohardness measurements indicate the following:

- (1) The average nanohardness value of RT deposited microlaminates (e.g., 4.0 GPa for Cu/Nb 1:1 system) is consistently higher than the nanohardness (e.g., 3.1 GPa for Cu/Nb 1:1 system) of films deposited at a 500°C substrate temperature, suggesting the presence of a relatively fine and dense substructure in RT deposited microlaminates.
- (2) Nanohardness measurements for Cu/Nb 100 nm/layer, 1:1 microlaminates are about 55% higher than the ROM value, suggesting an enhanced hardness due to the presence of fine grains (50-70 nm). In contrast, the average nanohardness values of both RT and high temperature deposited Cu/Nb 3:1 microlaminates (2.5 GPa and 1.8 GPa respectively) are close to the ROM value of 2.1 GPa, as the substructure consists of large (100-150 nm) grains and characteristic annealing twins.

Vickers Microhardness (H_V)—Vickers microhardness measurements of the Cu/Nb microlaminates were conducted at applied loads between 25 g and 200 g. At these applied loads, average indent depths in the 1:1 microlaminate were between 2.3 and 6 μm (i.e., deforming 11 to 28 bi-layers), which is 9 to 28% of the total microlaminate thickness. At these applied loads the nearly constant H_V values indicate that the microhardness values are apparently not influenced by

any substrate effect. During microindentation, the deformation process primarily leads to the closure of microvoids, and associated densification of the deformed layers without any cracks at the diagonals. These Vickers microhardness measurements show the following trends, similar to the nanohardness measurements:

- (1) Each RT deposited microlaminate exhibited higher hardness values than the microlaminates deposited at a 500°C substrate temperature.
- (2) Average Vickers hardness of the Cu/Nb 1:1, RT microlaminate ($H_V = 1.72$ GPa) was slightly greater than the ROM value ($H_V = 1.55$ GPa), whereas the Cu/Nb 3:1, RT microlaminate exhibited a $H_V = 1.52$ GPa, nearly equivalent to the ROM value ($H_V = 1.55$ GPa).

Yield Strength—During the tension tests the Cu/Nb 1:1 and 3:1 microlaminates, deposited at RT and 500°C, exhibited yield strength values between 122-167 MPa, and the elongation to failure between 8-12%. Based on the measured H_V test data, the apparent compressive yield strength of the Cu/Nb 3:1 RT microlaminate is 506 MPa and the compressive yield strength of the Cu/Nb 1:1 RT microlaminate is 573 MPa. Even with 25% and 50% Nb in these microlaminates, the yield strength values are closer to the yield strength value of wrought and pure Nb, suggesting that the enhanced strength of each microlaminate appears to be due to very small grains and thin layers of Nb, providing high deformation resistance in the microlaminates. These results also suggest that the Cu/Nb microlaminates constructed from alternating layers of Cu and Nb consist of a tight structure with very low porosity compared to thick, pure Cu and pure Nb films.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Copper/niobium microlaminates, because of their high strength and high conductivity properties are being developed for applications including high power generators, heat exchangers, and coils for high-field magnets. Using sputter deposition methodology, Cu/Nb microlaminates consisting of alternating layers of Cu and Nb were successfully produced and evaluated. These microlaminates included two different multilayer architectures: (1) Cu/Nb 1:1 i.e., 100 nm/layer each, and (2) Cu/Nb 3:1 i.e., 300 nm/layer Cu and 100 nm/layer Nb. Each laminate was produced by depositing the film materials on a Cu foil substrate held at either RT or 500°C. Based on a TEM/SAD study, both the Cu and Nb metal layers exhibited a polycrystalline structure in the as-deposited microlaminates at both substrate temperatures. Each microlaminate exhibited a columnar macrograin structure typical of films deposited at temperatures between 0.28 and 0.5 T_m .

Nanoindentation measurements of each microlaminate indicated that calculated elastic modulus values were similar to the values obtained by the ROM. The specific role of layer thickness (or volume percent Nb) and substrate temperature on the mechanical properties was evident both from the nanohardness and Vickers hardness measurements. Each RT deposited microlaminate exhibited higher hardness values than the microlaminates deposited at 500°C, suggesting the presence of a relatively fine and dense substructure in RT deposited microlaminates. Consistent with the ratio of constituents, the Cu/Nb 1:1 microlaminates exhibited higher hardness than the Cu/Nb 3:1 microlaminates. Overall, the Cu/Nb 1:1 RT microlaminate exhibited enhanced hardness compared to the ROM value, whereas the Cu/Nb 3:1 RT microlaminate exhibited hardness equivalent to the ROM value. Both the high hardness and yield strength measurements of the Cu/Nb microlaminates suggest that the as-deposited films exhibit mechanical properties generally higher than the ROM value obtained from the properties of wrought Cu and Nb materials, and also Cu/Nb microcomposites or laminates which involve multiple deformation processing steps in their production.

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Figure 1. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Photomicrograph Showing Columnar Morphology of As-Deposited Cu/Nb Microlaminates on a Cu Substrate

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Bright Field Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) Image Showing Multilayer Architecture of Microlaminates Constructed from Alternating Layers of Cu and Nb

(a) Cu/Nb 1:1, 100 nm Thick Layers, RT Deposition

(b) Cu/Nb 3:1, 300 nm Cu - 100 nm Nb Thick Layers, 500°C Deposition

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Selected Area Diffraction Patterns of As-deposited Cu/Nb Microlaminates

(a) Cu/Nb 1:1, RT

(b) Cu/Nb 1:1, 500°C

Figure 4. Calculated Elastic Modulus Values of As-Deposited Cu/Nb Microlaminates as Obtained by Nanoindentation

Figure 5. Measured Nanohardness Values of As-Deposited Cu/Nb Microlaminates

CHARACTERIZATION OF INTERFACES AND WHISKER/PARTICLE SYSTEMS
